

1 **Analysis of vulnerability assessment frameworks and** 2 **methodologies in urban areas**

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9

10 **Abstract** The occurrence of major natural disasters in recent years has impacted large
11 cities worldwide and boosted the need of assessing urban resilience. As a key factor of
12 resilience, vulnerability correlates attributes of communities with the level of damage
13 caused by hazards. Although a large amount of studies has reviewed the assessment of
14 vulnerability from the perspective of a particular hazard, the combined analysis involving
15 all kind of hazards and vulnerability dimensions in the urban context is uncommon. This
16 research provides a critical analysis of a selected sample of 72 contributions released from
17 1998 to 2018 and related to the appraisal of vulnerability, in order to determine their
18 adequacy in the evaluation of urban vulnerability. The findings stemming from this
19 process revealed that the social dimension was a priority, whilst qualitative components
20 associated with risk awareness were slightly covered. Furthermore, multi-criteria decision
21 analysis and weighting allocation were the most widely used techniques to address urban
22 vulnerability, whilst 32 methodologies were bespoke-built to be applied to particular
23 locations. Most of the cases examined were oriented to specific hazards, with only 10 of
24 them focused on multiple hazards. Hence, the results suggest the need for developing a
25 new framework applicable to multiple hazards worldwide to bridge the identified gaps.

26

27 **Keywords** Vulnerability; Resilience; Exposure; Disaster Risk; Hazards; Urbanization.

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Since 1998, the planet has suffered more than seven thousand natural disasters,
31 whereby 1,333,654 people have died and more than 4.4 billion people have been affected,
32 causing damages with an estimated value over 2.5 trillion USD (EMDAT, 2018). Most
33 of these disasters were located in urban areas due to the large concentration of population,
34 resources and activities. These figures highlight the role of disaster risk reduction in the
35 evolution of present communities, by enhancing risk understanding and awareness of the
36 most vulnerable groups (Thywissen, 2006), delimiting areas at risk and identifying
37 drivers that produce vulnerability and risk (Bogardi and Birkmann, 2004). In this vein,
38 the combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches is crucial to conduct disaster
39 risk reduction over the longer term (Birkmann and Wisner, 2006). Whilst quantitative
40 approaches serve to estimate the spatial and temporal potential impacts of disaster risks
41 across a set of indicators, metrics or frameworks, qualitative frameworks are immerse in
42 explaining the motivation of people to be engaged in preventive measures through the
43 perception of hazard severity and occurrence, as well as the efficacy of protective
44 response (Reischl et al., 2018).

45 Risk is the probability of occurrence of a loss impacting environmental, economic or
46 societal dimensions resulting from natural or human-induced hazards (Alexander, 2000).

47 Risk mainly depends on the close relationship among three factors, namely hazard,
48 vulnerability and exposure. Since risk associates the likelihood of occurrence of a hazard
49 with its consequences (UNISDR, 2009), it can also be deemed as a function of two
50 variables represented by the hazard event and the vulnerability of the elements exposed

51 (Birkmann, 2007). When society is unable to cope with the effects derived from hazards
52 using its own resources exclusively, a severe disruption of its functioning produces
53 extensive human, material or environmental losses, resulting in a situation which is
54 defined as a disaster (EEA, 2018). Cardona (2003) underlined the necessary correlation
55 between intensity, specific location and period of exposure to properly refer to hazards.
56 However, Burton (1993) states that hazard is the result of the interaction between natural
57 and social systems, whereas Cutter (2001) considers hazards as a threat to people and the
58 things they value.

59 As a further component of disaster risk, exposure refers to everything that can be
60 affected in an area where a hazard event may occur (Cardona, 1990). Fuchs et al. (2011)
61 considers exposure as a crucial element of vulnerability, being a necessary but yet not
62 sufficient determinant of risk. On the contrary, exposure is a prerequisite of vulnerability
63 (Cardona et al., 2012). Despite vulnerability has been traditionally associated with
64 physical fragility (Bankoff et al., 2004), it depends on multiple variables mainly covering
65 physical, social, economic, cultural and environmental dimensions that vary across
66 temporal and spatial scales. Vulnerability refers to the predisposition of exposed elements
67 to be negatively impacted when hazard events occur (Bogardi and Birkmann, 2004;
68 UNISDR, 2004; Birkmann and Wisner, 2006; ADRC, 2009). Diverse interpretations of
69 this concept are founded on Climate Change as a hazard. According to the
70 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2001), vulnerability determines the extent
71 of damage caused by Climate Change that a system can sustain. Adger (2006) define
72 vulnerability as the result of a wide range of studies based on different climate scenarios
73 to identify future adaptive strategies.

74 As a consequence of the multidimensional nature of vulnerability, it can be divided
75 into various categories, inter alia, physical, social and economic vulnerability

76 (Schmidtlein et al., 2008). Physical vulnerability contemplates the properties of physical
77 elements that determine their prospective damage in case of a hazard event (Ebert et al.,
78 2009). The constraints of a community that affect its capacity to cope with the effects of
79 hazards shape social vulnerability (Hummell et al., 2016). Unlike physical vulnerability,
80 social vulnerability does not rely on the type of hazard. Economic vulnerability refers to
81 the incapacity of people to face a particular threat impacting their livelihoods (UNISDR,
82 2015).

83 There is no global consensus to define urban areas due to the consideration of
84 additional factors such as population size, density, economic occupation or urban
85 functions to characterize urban settings, as well as the changes made by different
86 countries to classify urban areas over time. Among many existing definitions, Lopez-
87 Moreno (2017) devises urban agglomeration as “*the population contained within the*
88 *contours of a contiguous territory inhabited at urban density levels without regard to*
89 *administrative boundaries*”. The degree to which socio-economic systems and physical
90 assets in urban areas are susceptible to and able to cope with adverse effects of a single
91 or several hazards is known as urban vulnerability (Thywissen, 2006).

92 The measurement of urban vulnerability has been the target of numerous studies in
93 the literature. Barbat et al. (2010) discussed seismic vulnerability over a period of 15
94 years. Multi-scale flooding vulnerability assessments caused by hydro-meteorological
95 hazards were conducted by Ciurean et al. (2017) and Papathoma-Köhle et al. (2017).
96 Tsunami vulnerability was examined by Tarbotton et al. (2015) in the last decade to
97 develop empirical vulnerability functions. Vamvatsikos et al. (2010) completed a review
98 of structural vulnerability assessments under earthquake, flooding and tsunami hazards.
99 To broaden the study of community vulnerability field under the impact of different

100 hazards, this article presented an analysis of urban vulnerability assessment methods to
101 ascertain their suitability.

102 The structure of the manuscript encompasses four additional sections. Firstly, a state-
103 of-the-art on vulnerability assessment methods is presented. Then, the research method is
104 described, covering the sampling and the analysis criteria. The presentation of results
105 obtained from the research and their discussion form the next section. Lastly, the
106 conclusions of the article are summarized.

107

108 **2. Vulnerability assessment methods**

109

110 The use of models and frameworks to appraise vulnerability is hampered by the
111 breadth and complexity of the term (Twigg and Mihir, 1998), which embraces various
112 dimensions including economic, demographic, psychological, political or physical
113 aspects, among others. Moreover, the factors impacting vulnerability are mainly rooted
114 in a complex and diverse aggregate as society, which varies in different ways over time
115 and space. In this section, several global approaches to gauge vulnerability from different
116 perspectives were described to emphasize the difficulty of covering all variables and
117 components involved in the assessment of vulnerability.

118 The Disaster Risk Index (DRI) was developed by the UN Development Programme
119 to compare disaster risk between countries exposed to hazards (UNDP, 2004). As part of
120 the DRI, a relative vulnerability measure was calculated as the quotient between the
121 amount of fatalities and the exposed population (UNDP, 2004). The recognition of
122 vulnerable areas to hazards by comparing risk levels considering individual and multi-
123 hazard risks at regional and national level was the aim of the initiative known as the
124 Identification of Global Natural Disaster Risk Hotspots. Mortality-related risk, total and

125 relative economic losses were the three indicators deemed by the Hotspots Project (Dilley
126 et al., 2005). At national scale, the Prevalent Vulnerability Index is a metric constructed
127 from a set of indicators that cover social, economic, environmental or demographic
128 dimensions to measure tangible and intangible effects derived from hazard events
129 affecting a given country (Cardona, 2008). It is also necessary to highlight some further
130 developments in the field, such as the Bogardi, Birkmann and Cardona (BBC) conceptual
131 framework (Bogardi and Birkmann, 2004; Cardona, 1999; Cardona, 2001) and the
132 Pressure and Release model (Blaikie et al., 1994). The former consists of a holistic
133 approach encompassing the three sustainable dimensions, human security and
134 vulnerability to quantify environmental impacts in relation to the holistic sustainable
135 development concept (Birkmann, 2008). On the original basis of Chambers (1989), the
136 Pressure and Release model explains vulnerability by analysing disasters under a three-
137 fold aspect: root causes, dynamic pressures and unsafe condition.

138 Vulnerability has also been handled from a biased point of view. For instance, the
139 Composite Vulnerability Index evaluates external economic factors and environmental
140 hazards to measure vulnerability by means of a set of weighted indicators previously
141 selected (Mazzi et al., 2001). Hazard vulnerability in U.S. counties is examined by the
142 Social Vulnerability Index (SoVI) through the assessment of 11 variables related to socio-
143 economic and demographic dimensions (Cutter et al., 2003). At sub-county scale,
144 vulnerability is determined by the Spatially Explicit Resilience-Vulnerability model that
145 evaluates aspects such as exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity through diverse
146 spatial, socio-economic and place-specific indicators (Frazier et al., 2014).

147 The European Commission funded the project Climate Change and Urban
148 Vulnerability in Africa to estimate the impact of Climate Change as a hazard at urban
149 scale on Africa until 2050 by evaluating the vulnerability of societies, urban ecosystems

150 and urban-rural interfaces and the urban built environment, as well as institutional
151 adaptation measures under the threat of floods, droughts, heat waves and sea-level rise
152 hazards (EU, 2010)

153 **3. Research method**

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155 The research methodology considered in this article comprises the procedures for
156 selecting the sample size of the publications to include in the literature review and the
157 thorough analysis of their contents under different prisms, as described in the following
158 subsections.

159

160 **3.1. Sampling**

161

162 An extensive literature review was undertaken in order to select suitable references
163 related to vulnerability assessment frameworks applied in urban areas. As reflected in
164 [Figure 1](#), the sample process encompassed four stages. The initial search was conducted
165 through the scientific database Scopus. Since more than 20 years has been found as a long
166 period of time to extract relevant conclusions (Jato-Espino et al., 2014), the quest was
167 extended from 1998 to 2018.

168

Figure 1. Approach taken to select contributions

Boolean functions were applied to the combination of keywords such as Disaster Risk OR Vulnerability Assessment AND Urban, to scrutinize all the fields covered by the database. 3,954 contributions were elicited as a result of this primary search. In the sorting phase, further constraints were incorporated into the searching criteria. Thus, the subject area was limited to Environmental Sciences, Engineering and Earth and Planetary Sciences. Moreover, only original articles, review articles and conference proceedings in English language were qualified. Hence, 2,173 references met the requirements of this stage.

Then, an analysis of title, abstract and keywords by manual screening was performed to identify all the documents addressed to the urban realm and covering a comprehensive approach of vulnerability assessment frameworks. In doing so, the number of adequate contributions was reduced to 271 documents in the third step. The full text of these manuscripts was revised in detail to ascertain its alignment with the scope of the research

185 and its relevancy to be qualified as final contributions. After ending the sampling process,
186 72 references published in 43 journals were finally selected. The distribution of articles
187 among journals was uneven. Natural Hazards was the largest contributor with 19 articles.
188 Disasters provided 4 items, whilst the Journal of Disaster Risk Studies and Natural
189 Hazards and Earth System Sciences only accounted for 3 documents each. The
190 International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction, the International Journal of Disaster
191 Resilience in the Built Environment, Applied Geography and Chinese Geographical
192 Science published 2 articles each. The remaining papers were equally shared between
193 other journals.

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195 **3.2. Analysis of the information**

196

197 After the completion of the sampling process, a profound analysis of the selected
198 references was conducted to determine the suitability of existing frameworks to
199 accurately appraise urban vulnerability under the effect of any sort of hazard. In addition,
200 the participation of social stakeholder groups and the implementation of methodologies
201 covering all aspects of vulnerability were also examined. In this vein, three questions
202 were addressed to lead the discussion of the items collected: (Q1) How determinant is the
203 typology of hazard in the development of urban vulnerability assessments?; (Q2) How
204 are the qualitative components of vulnerability evaluated?; (Q3) What methodologies are
205 used to develop vulnerability assessment frameworks? Arguments to these questions are
206 presented in the next subsection. Moreover, all the publications were also categorized
207 according to diverse aspects, such as spatial and temporal distribution, criteria used to set
208 indicators, stakeholders' involvement and vulnerability components enclosed in the
209 frameworks.

210

211 **4. Results and discussion**

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213 This section presents the results obtained from the analysis of 72 contributions
214 involved in the assessment of vulnerability in urban areas between 1998 and 2018. Hence,
215 first is the exploration of the context, components of the vulnerability assessment
216 frameworks and techniques used by these tools. Then, the questions raised in the
217 methodology section about the use of vulnerability assessment frameworks in the
218 publications compiled are responded one by one.

219

220 **4.1. Context**

221

222 There are no general patterns applicable to all contexts. Different elements influence
223 the assessment of vulnerability covered by these 72 contributions. Among them, this
224 study considered four aspects to be discussed. First, the interpretation of the concept of
225 vulnerability leading to different approaches. Second, the dimensions explored by the
226 distinct frameworks. Third, the range of hazards covered by the reviewed contributions
227 and lastly, the timing and geographical distribution of the case studies examined.

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229 **4.1.1. Different perspectives of vulnerability**

230

231 The literature on vulnerability reflects several usages of the concept as shown in [Table](#)
232 [1](#), due to its great complexity that produces a broad spectrum of assessment
233 methodologies at household, local, regional or national levels. Exposure, sensitivity and
234 adaptive capacity as key drivers of vulnerability are also connected with societal assets

235 through their proximity to hazards, the impacts caused by hazards or the adaptation to
 236 hazard effects, respectively (Frazier, 2014). Furthermore, vulnerability has been the
 237 subject of study by two distinct schools of thought. Whilst the Climate Change adaptation
 238 school aims at finding the most efficient adaptation way to hazards, the disaster risk
 239 reduction school is primarily focused on risk reduction actions (Romieu et al., 2010).
 240 Regarding the analyzed manuscripts, only 11 were part of the former school, with the
 241 remaining 61 aligned with the latter movement.

242
 243 **Table 1.** Approaches of vulnerability definition

Definition	Sources
<i>"The propensity of exposed elements such as human beings, their livelihoods, and assets to suffer adverse effects when impacted by hazard events"</i>	Cardona, 1990; Blaikie et al., 1994; Bogardi and Birkmann, 2004; UNISDR, 2004
<i>"The degree of loss to a given element at risk (or set of elements) resulting from a given hazard at a given severity level"</i>	UNDHA, 1992
<i>"The extent to which a natural or social system is susceptible to sustaining damage from climate change"</i>	IPCC, 2001
<i>"A situation-specific, interacting with a hazard event to generate risk"</i>	Cutter et al., 2003
<i>"The inherent weakness in certain aspects of the environment with are susceptible to harm due to social, biophysical, or design characteristics"</i>	Rashed and Weeks, 2003
<i>"The condition or process resulting from physical, social, economic and environmental factors, which determine the likelihood and scale of damage from the impact of a given hazard"</i>	UNDP, 2004
<i>"The degree of experienced loss of life and economic damage"</i>	Dilley et al., 2005
<i>"The state of susceptibility to harm from exposure to stresses associated with environmental and social change and from the absence of capacity to adapt"</i>	Adger, 2006
<i>"The predisposition, susceptibilities, fragilities, weaknesses, deficiencies, or lack of capacities that favor adverse effects on the exposed elements"</i>	Thywissen, 2006
<i>"The characteristics and circumstances of a community, system or asset that make it susceptible to the damaging effects of a hazard"</i>	UNISDR, 2009
<i>"Inherent characteristics of a system that create the potential for harm but are independent of the probabilistic risk of occurrence of any particular hazard or extreme event"</i>	Modica and Zoboli, 2016
<i>"The potential of physical impacts on built-up environment or infrastructure and population"</i>	Hizbaron et al., 2018

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245 **4.1.2. Aspects regarded by the selected contributions**

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247 In general, vulnerability predominantly comprises four main aspects: physical, social,
 248 economic and environmental, such that they interact to each other, increasing the
 249 susceptibility of communities to hazards effects (Adger, 2006). Nevertheless, further
 250 aspects can also be deemed in the assessment of vulnerability. Schneiderbauer et al.

251 (2013) emphasized the psychological aspect after the occurrence of hazards and
252 Birkmann and Wisner (2006) highlighted ecological vulnerability as the relationship
253 between human activities and ecosystem functions.

254 Figure 2 shows the distribution of aspects covered by the selected references per
255 continent. The social (64), physical (57) and economic (54) facets were the most
256 examined ones. On the contrary, psychological (Salami et al., 2017), technical (Sadeghi-
257 Pouya, 2017), taxation (Tavares et al., 2017), ecological (Römer et al., 2012; Ahmed and
258 Kelman, 2018), cultural (Jackson et al., 2017; Ahmed and Kelman, 2018) and historical
259 (Aragon-Durand, 2007; Jackson et al., 2017) aspects were less considered. Demographic,
260 environmental and institutional issues were assessed 20, 19 and 7 times, respectively. The
261 social matter was the most studied factor in Africa (8), America (14) and Europe (15),
262 whilst Asia (26) and Oceania (5) were mainly focused on the physical and economic
263 fields, respectively.

Figure 2. Breakdown of the analyzed aspects of urban vulnerability by continent

4.1.3. Hazards involved in the review

As a consequence of the close interrelation between risk, hazard and vulnerability (Blaikie et al., 1994), the role of hazards must be thoroughly analyzed in the assessment of vulnerability. Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of hazards considered by the 72 selected references according to the continent where the case studies were located. The review disclosed that flooding (23), earthquakes (16) and landslides (11) were the most examined hazards. Whilst Europe collected the highest amount of studies based on landslides (7) and flooding (6), Asia oriented most of its contributions to the discussion of the assessment of vulnerability due to seismic (7), flooding (6) and multiple hazards (4). Flooding was also the preferred hazard in investigations undertaken in America, Africa and Oceania. Furthermore, other less common hazards were also examined. Reischl et al.

279 (2018) evaluated urban vulnerability due to heatwaves in Graz. Bushfire risk was
 280 addressed by Solangaarachchi et al. (2012) in Sydney. Volcanic (Hizbaron et al., 2018)
 281 and drought (Kim et al., 2015) hazards substantiated two case studies in East Java and
 282 Seoul, respectively. Lastly, Sherly et al. (2015) and Sanchez et al. (2018) led studies based
 283 on technological and human-induced hazards.

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Figure 3. Dissemination of hazards by continent

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Regarding the question (Q1) How determinant is the typology of hazard in the development of urban vulnerability assessments? Most of the reviewed contributions focused on vulnerability derived from a particular hazard (Figure 3). Ten references, published from 2008 to 2017, addressed the topic from a comprehensive point of view, encompassing all kinds of hazards. China (3) and Chile (2) were the countries that hosted the highest number of case studies. The analysed methodologies expressed a preference for quantitative indicators (5) and literature review (6) as the source to define the components of their frameworks. Although three references involved qualitative metrics, the participation of stakeholders was scarce. The Analytic Hierarchical Process (AHP) (2) and Factor Analysis (1) were the most widely used established techniques, in contrast

298 with five bespoke methodologies built by scholars. The remaining two publications
299 weighted indicators by direct allocation. Furthermore, the findings revealed that more
300 than 90% of the analysed literature considered from 0 to 5 indicators specifically
301 addressed to a particular hazard. Consequently, the type of hazard was not a pivotal factor
302 for the selected contributions to develop methodologies to gauge vulnerability. The
303 content of [Table 1](#) shapes vulnerability as an integral concept that should comprise all
304 hazards without distinction.

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306 **4.1.4. Spatiotemporal patterns of the case studies reviewed**

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308 A total of 42 countries representing all continents contributed to this research, which
309 comprises 82 different case studies as shown in [Figure 4](#). Whilst Asia and Europe
310 involved 12 different countries each gathering 31 and 23 case studies, respectively,
311 America and Africa regarded 9 and 6 nations covering 17 and 7 assessments each.
312 Oceania only included 3 regions with 4 case studies, among which half of them
313 corresponded to Australia. India (10) presented the greatest number of studies in Asia,
314 followed by the United States in America and Turkey in Europe with 4 each. Most case
315 studies in Africa were located in Nigeria (2).

316 According to the [EMDAT \(2018\)](#) statistics between 1998 and 2018, Asia showed the
317 highest amount of deaths caused by disasters (843,418), followed by America (322,636).
318 Europe and Africa suffered 140,000 human losses, whilst Oceania was the least impacted
319 continent with 4,915 fatalities. As reflected in [Table 2](#), the United States experienced the
320 largest number of disasters (504) causing the greatest damage over the study period
321 (almost 897 billion dollars). Although the occurrence of disasters in India was inferior
322 (362), Indian population was the most impacted one in the Planet in terms of fatalities
323 (99,843), as well as affected (1,113,584,646) and homeless (14,433,492) people.

324

325 **Table 2.** Statistics of countries with the highest number of case studies per continent (EMDAT, 2018)

Country	Occurrence	Fatalities	Affected	Homeless	Damage ('000 USD)
Australia	112	850	439,961	15,595	37,467,154
India	362	99,843	1,113,584,646	14,433,492	74,683,361
Nigeria	100	11,155	11,472,658	182,302	847,922
The United States	504	7,989	112,485,925	296,540	896,801,110
Turkey	78	19,633	4,241,812	942,561	26,057,000

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Figure 4. Geographical distribution of case studies by countries and continents

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330 Inland cities were represented by 32 case studies, in contrast with the 50 assessments
 331 of coastal areas. According to their population, urban areas were divided into four groups:
 332 small (less than 100,000 people), medium (from 100,000 to 1.5 million residents), large
 333 (from 1.5 to 10 million inhabitants) and megacities (more than 10 million population). As
 334 reflected in [Figure 5a](#), large and medium cities accounted for 33 and 31 studies each. By
 335 contrast, small towns and megacities only achieved 14 and 4 cases, respectively.
 336 Furthermore, the 61 studies corresponding to the local scale predominated over the
 337 regional (14) and national (7) levels ([Figure 5b](#)).

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339 **Figure 5.** Distribution of case studies by (a) City size and (b) Scale

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Regarding the time series shown in [Figure 6](#), the publishing trend has slowly increased from 2007 to nowadays, but never exceeding 12 annual publications. Instead, no contributions were recorded from 1998 to 2006, apart from those produced in 2003. Data from [EMDAT \(2018\)](#) reflected that during 2010, Africa and America suffered the highest damages and human losses in the period covered by this research. Furthermore, 2003 and 2004 were the worst years in terms of major disasters occurred in Europe and Asia, respectively, whilst Oceania faced the toughest year in 2009. These statistics are not correlated to the production of literature related to the assessment of urban vulnerability.

The findings achieved also disclosed a significant evolution in the appraisal of vulnerability during the study period. From 2003 to 2008 inclusively, literature was focused on a single type of hazard and no metrics nor frameworks were developed. These outcomes predominantly contributed to enhance risk awareness of urban population. Years 2009 and 2010 represented a milestone in the field of vulnerability. Multiple hazards, the use of AHP and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) were firstly considered by researchers in 2009, whilst the following year meant the addition of qualitative indicators in assessments, the participation of stakeholder groups in their characterization and the incorporation of further vulnerability dimensions to supplement physical and social ones. In recent years, the contributions showed a balance in the use of

359 qualitative/quantitative metrics and GIS, a preference in the analysis of specific hazards
 360 and a high level of stakeholders involvement. Although the socio-economic dimension
 361 prevails in the selected references, further vulnerability aspects were also contemplated.
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363
 364 **Figure 6.** Distribution of contributions on urban vulnerability per year (1998-2018)

365 4.2. Components of vulnerability assessment frameworks

367
 368 Figure 7 illustrates the amount of indicators covered by the 72 selected references. The
 369 largest numerous group (20) ranged from 0 to 5 metrics, followed by the categories that
 370 encompassed from 16 to 20 and 6 to 10 indicators with 13 and 12 contributions,
 371 respectively. No metrics in the assessment of vulnerability were revealed by 16
 372 references, which predominantly focused on, inter alia, determine risk & hazard
 373 awareness (Nathan, 2008; Oteng-Ababio, 2012), provide effective mitigation practices
 374 (Sonmez Saner, 2015), define implications in urban planning (Chunliang et al., 2011) or
 375 develop policies (Mustafa et al., 2010). Similarly, 65 contributions exhibited until 5
 376 indicators in close liaison with the involved hazards. A range from 6 to 10 hazard-related
 377 parameters was considered by the rest of references.

378 Although the measurement of qualitative indicators is difficult, the assessment of
 379 vulnerability requires the combined use of quantitative and qualitative approaches to

380 capture all its tangible and intangible facets. In order to answer the question (Q2) How
 381 are the qualitative components of vulnerability evaluated?, this research unveiled that 36
 382 contributions deemed just quantitative metrics whilst only 2 of them were exclusively
 383 focused on qualitative indicators (Hernandez and Ruiz, 2016; Cerchiello et al., 2018).
 384 Both qualitative and quantitative parameters were comprised by 17 references. The
 385 remaining publications lacked any class of metrics, since they are based on bespoke
 386 methodologies built by experts. The participation of stakeholder groups is highly
 387 necessary to characterize qualitative indicators mostly associated to adaptive capacity and
 388 risk perception. In this regard, householders (14) were the main respondents, followed by
 389 local administration (Hassel, 2012; Cerchiello et al., 2018), staff and expert interviews
 390 (Chunliang et al., 2011; Ahmed and Kelman, 2018) and community leaders (Andrade and
 391 Szlafsztein, 2018). The contribution of the studied references to social learning disclosed
 392 7 references focused on hazards and risk awareness. Training in risk prevention and
 393 preparation was addressed by Oteng-Ababio (2012), Salami et al. (2017), Cerchiello et
 394 al. (2018) and Reischl et al. (2018).

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 397 **Figure 7.** Sharing of references according to the range of total indicators used

398
 399 Diverse methods were used to select the components assessed in the examined
 400 references as shown in Figure 8. Literature review was the most preferred mode (38) of

401 determining indicators, followed by experts' judgment (9). The availability of data was
 402 the critical factor to set metrics in [Chunliang et al. \(2011\)](#), [Wilhelmi and Morss \(2013\)](#),
 403 [Kim et al. \(2015\)](#), [Sherly et al. \(2015\)](#), [Cankaya et al. \(2016\)](#) and [Hizbaron et al. \(2018\)](#).
 404 Some references were based on the adaption of existing frameworks such as Risk-UE
 405 ([Cherif et al., 2017](#)) and the SoVI ([Solangaarachchi et al., 2012](#); [Huang et al., 2015](#);
 406 [Sherbinin and Bardy, 2015](#); [Roncancio and Nardocci, 2016](#); [Eid and El-adaway, 2017](#)).
 407 The Delphi method was employed by [Armas \(2012\)](#) and [Yuan et al. \(2015\)](#). [Sdao et al.](#)
 408 [\(2011\)](#) applied a mathematical model to gauge the vulnerability of Potenza to landslide
 409 and flooding hazards.

410
 411 **Figure 8.** Criteria employed to select the indicators forming the vulnerability assessment frameworks

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 413 The sources of information that served to appraise the indicators in the selected
 414 contributions are reflected in Figure 9. Data for vulnerability assessment were principally
 415 assembled from census (45), householders' questionnaires (17) and remote sensing and
 416 satellite imagery (10). Furthermore, experimental data ([Torres-Vera and Canas, 2003](#))
 417 and both questionnaires ([Debnath, 2013](#); [Eidsvig et al., 2014](#); [Ahmed and Kelman, 2018](#);
 418 [Alizadeh et al., 2018](#); [Cerchiello et al., 2018](#)) and interviews ([Reischl et al., 2018](#))
 419 addressed to experts completed the main ways of gathering data. Field observation data
 420 were used in [Sonmez Saner \(2015\)](#), [Cherif et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Salami et al. \(2017\)](#).

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Figure 9. Data sources used to assess indicators in the contributions reviewed

4.3. Techniques used in the contributions evaluated

Figure 10 shows the large variety of approaches employed by the selected contributions, excluding 32 of them that followed bespoke methodologies developed by experts. Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods were represented by the Analytic Hierarchical Process (AHP) with 10 references (Ebert et al., 2009; Chunliang et al., 2011; Armas, 2012; Martins et al., 2012; Walker et al., 2014; Nath et al., 2015; Cankaya et al., 2016; Fernandez et al., 2016; Sadrykia et al., 2017; Tavares et al., 2017), the Analytic Network Process (ANP) (Alizadeh et al., 2018) and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) (Sadrykia et al., 2017). Whilst the first two methods are based on human judgments to assign weights, the latter chooses the closest alternative to an ideal solution. Factor analysis was used to find random variables (factors) that can integrate all variables (Huang et al., 2015; Eid and El-Adaway, 2017; Tavares et al., 2017). The identification of principal components that are linear combinations of indicators and the loading of each variable on just one principal component was the reason why Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was employed (Khan, 2012; Solangaarachchi et al., 2012; Sherbinin and Bardy, 2015; Tavares et al., 2017; Sanchez et al., 2018). Weighted linear combination was used to allocate weights

443 according the relevance of indicators (Martins et al., 2012; Yeganeh and Sabri, 2014).
444 Spatial multi-criteria evaluation combined statistical and spatial approaches in Hizbaron
445 et al. (2018) and Ahmed and Kelman (2018). The use of indices associated to particular
446 hazards (Kim et al., 2015) may involve that underlying vulnerability factors are
447 disregarded.

448 The literature reviewed made also extensive use of the assignment of weights to
449 indicators. Equal weights to all metrics were given by 8 references, whilst others were
450 allocated by the authors/experts or accordingly to indices such as the effective drought
451 index. Further minority methods such as Pressure and Release (Chen et al., 2014),
452 Maximum Flux Principle (Liu et al., 2015), Data Envelopment Analysis (Sherly et al.,
453 2015), cluster analysis (Chang et al., 2018), statistical tests (Yuan et al., 2015) and
454 Bayesian joint conditional probability (Espada et al., 2017) also served to appraise
455 vulnerability. The application of fuzzy logic as a method to deal with uncertainty was
456 only contemplated by Martins et al. (2012), Yeganeh and Sabri (2014), Espada et al.
457 (2017) and Sadrykia et al. (2017). Furthermore, Sadrykia et al. (2017) and Sadeghi-Pouya
458 et al. (2017) studied the influence of changing the weights in the final results produced
459 by the assessments through sensitivity analysis. Lastly, the use of GIS was perceived in
460 44 out of the 72 references analysed.

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Figure 10. Techniques used in the selected references

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As reflected in Figure 10, there is no general consensus on the methodologies followed by authors of the selected contributions to appraise vulnerability with respect to the question (Q3) What methodologies are used to develop vulnerability assessment frameworks? Although the methods of 32 references were customized to be used for the analysis of particular cases, two main streams of techniques are distinguished, such as multi-criteria decision-making methods and the direct allocation of weights according to diverse criteria. In both cases, a degree of subjectivity is perceived (Chen et al., 2013). Simplicity, the subjectivity of weighting procedures or the unavailability of data are the main arguments in favour of the assignation of equal weights (Clark et al., 1998). However, Mustafa et al. (2010), Basaran-Uysal et al. (2014), Eidsvig et al. (2014) preferred to allocate weights according to their preferences and Kienberger (2012) employed experts' judgement.

Imprecision and uncertainty are intrinsically associated with vulnerability assessments requiring the use of random variables linked to known probability distributions. Hence,

479 the introduction of fuzzy numbers as a recognized uncertainty method can provide an
480 applicable solution for vague phenomena. However, uncertainty was seldom addressed
481 by the references examined.

482 **4.4. Remarks about the selected publications**

483 Some aspects observed in the 72 publications reviewed are discussed below by
484 considering them grouped into the five major geographical areas. Most case studies
485 involving African countries were concentrated on the analysis of physical and social
486 dimensions. Whilst the former did not result in any metrics, the latter devised two social
487 vulnerability indices through the participation of stakeholders, leading to some
488 implications at national level related to the presence and availability of early warning
489 systems, the linkage between sensitivity to hazards and complex socio-economic
490 conditions and the need of legislation covering preparedness for and response to hazards.
491 Physical assessments hinted at inter alia, the development of new building codes and
492 regulations and the prohibition on building at inappropriate spots.

493 A wide spectrum of varied methodologies was used to explore vulnerability in
494 Oceania. Efficient urban strategies were proposed in Australia by integrating Disaster
495 Risk Reduction and Climate Adaptation notions into a spatially explicit analytical
496 technique, whilst the joint consideration of exposure, susceptibility (social, economic,
497 physical and so forth) and the paucity of resilience grounded a new framework to
498 understand vulnerability to coastal hazard in Vanuatu. The identification of vulnerable
499 groups and urban areas was the aim of social vulnerability assessments, in order to adopt
500 measures for hazard mitigation and adaptation.

501 Concerning the American region, social vulnerability indices were developed in
502 Argentina and Mexico by classifying social conditions of local population. Analogous
503 vulnerability perceptions were gathered from Bolivian community leaders and local

504 authorities' surveys, in contrast with the difficulty to define strategies to cope with
505 hazards in Brazil due to social fragmentation. In this vein, spatial fragmentation of urban
506 areas founded the vulnerability assessment of Santiago in Chile and Tegucigalpa in
507 Honduras. The search for commonalities in Canadian communities served to determine
508 how they may be affected by hazards, whilst the study of travel distance to hospitals and
509 trauma centres helped build a multi-criteria evaluation model of earthquake vulnerability
510 in Victoria. Several maps presenting the distribution of vulnerable population within high
511 vulnerability areas were produced in the States by different means, such as the integration
512 of meteorological information with environmental and social data using GIS, the
513 involvement of residents in surveys and the use of census data. However, outstanding
514 data limitations were encountered.

515 The assessment of vulnerability in Asian cities was characterized by the high level of
516 population engaged in the process. Thus, the combination of quantitative/qualitative data
517 with participatory appraisal tools and remote sensing data with GIS promoted policies to
518 enhance vulnerable communities and develop flooding hazard maps in Bangladesh and
519 Thailand, respectively. The application of spatial multi-criteria evaluation in Indonesia
520 and Malaysia provided several scenarios to predict future uncertainties in the case of
521 volcanic and flooding hazards. Local questionnaires in Pakistan and Palestine fostered
522 the creation of mitigation plans and drafted policies to reduce seismic risk. Vulnerable
523 groups were identified in Philippines and South Korea using household surveys and
524 socio-economic databases. The selection of indicators according to data availability and
525 the construction of quantitative index systems served to draw the distribution of urban
526 economic and social vulnerability in China, as well as to provide scientific basis for policy
527 making. Sophisticated models were formulated in Iran by involving fuzzy logic, Artificial
528 Neural Network, sensitivity analysis, AHP, ANP, TOPSIS and GIS to evaluate social,

529 economic, physical and environmental factors. Vulnerability maps were proposed as a
530 result. Household survey data was the primary source for defining spatial mapping of
531 social vulnerability in Indian cities.

532 Europe revealed distinct methodologies to examine urban vulnerability. A set of
533 qualitative and quantitative parameters ranked from 1 to 5 was instrumental in
534 determining the socioeconomic vulnerability of multiple cities in Andorra, France,
535 Greece, Norway and Romania. Vulnerability in the Spanish city of Barcelona was
536 measured by analyzing the exposure of pipelines to earthquakes, whilst remote sensing
537 data was used to map flood-prone areas of Dresden in Germany. Furthermore, general
538 learning outcomes in terms of risk perceptions were obtained from expert interviews in
539 Austria and Sweden. Existing vulnerability frameworks, namely PEARL and Ensure
540 defined social and physical vulnerability zones in some Italian cities. Additionally, other
541 methodologies in the same country were founded on remote sensing data and a systemic
542 vulnerability analysis that relates the magnitude of extreme events with their
543 consequences on urban areas. Multicriteria decision analysis (AHP) and GIS fed by
544 statistical data shaped social vulnerability scenarios in Portugal. Physical vulnerability
545 assessments were predominant in Turkey through the analysis of remote sensing data.

546

547 **5. Conclusions**

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549 This article reviewed the assessment of vulnerability in urban areas by examining a
550 selected sample of 72 contributions published from 1998 to 2018 that included 82 case
551 studies located in 42 countries worldwide. The main conclusions drawn from this research
552 are summarized as follows:

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- 554 • The largest number of references were published in the last 10 years, 32 of them
555 from 2016 until today. As such, this research field is still emerging and expected
556 to keep growing in the future.
- 557 • The social dimension was the most considered aspect, exhibiting an uneven
558 geographical preference. There was no robust correlation between the level of
559 social concern and the per capita income of the countries or the statistics about
560 damages/human losses of the disasters occurred.
- 561 • Most of the contributions undertook the assessment of vulnerability under the
562 perspective of only a particular kind of hazard. By contrast, 14% of references
563 were focused on multiple hazards.
- 564 • A wide range of methodologies served to gauge vulnerability, but more than 44%
565 of the techniques used were customized to examine particular case studies. Multi-
566 criteria decision analysis and weighting allocation were the most commonly used
567 approaches. Uncertainty was barely deemed in the explored literature.
- 568 • Those frameworks comprising until 20 indicators were the most numerous (52).
569 Literature review and census data were the favourite information sources and
570 modes for determining parameters.
- 571 • The participation of stakeholders reduces the subjective nature of selecting
572 indicators through literature review. However, the diversity in the individuals
573 engaged in the determination and evaluation of intangible variables reflected
574 disparities in the outcomes.
- 575 • 19 references covered, either in whole or in part, qualitative parameters in the
576 appraisal of vulnerability. However, only 7 contributions led to enhance risk
577 perception or mitigation strategies of population.

578 • The case studies reviewed were mostly focused on coastal areas with a population
579 ranging from 1.5 to 10 million inhabitants. Hence vulnerability assessments were
580 mainly conducted at a local scale.

581 The main limitations of this research were the great variety of methodologies followed
582 by the references studied and the exclusive consideration of most contributions towards
583 a particular hazard. The conclusions extracted from this article identified several gaps to
584 be bridged by the development of a new holistic vulnerability assessment framework
585 globally applicable for all type of hazards whereby qualitative factors are covered with
586 the participation of people, both individually and collectively.

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